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Stability and Calibration Performance of Standard Platinum-Cobalt Resistance Thermometers for Cryogenic Applications

Yaonan Song^{1,2}, Haiyang Zhang^{1,2,3*}, Siqu Liu^{1,2}, Guoxin Li^{1,2,3}, Bo Gao^{1,2,3*}, Fuhong Li⁴, Fernando Sparasci^{5,2}, Laurent Pitre^{5,2}

¹ State Key Laboratory of Cryogenic Science and Technology, Technical Institute of Physics and Chemistry (TIPC), Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS), Beijing 100190, China

² TIPC-LNE Joint Laboratory on Cryogenic Metrology Science and Technology, Technical Institute of Physics and Chemistry (TIPC), Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS), Beijing 100190, China

³ University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100490, China

⁴ Yunnan Dafang Meter Limited Company, Kunming, China

⁵ Laboratoire National de Métrologie et d'Essais-Conservatoire National des Arts et Métiers (LNE-CNAM), F93210, La Plaine-Saint Denis, France

*Corresponding author, E-mail: zhy110@mail.ipc.ac.cn; bgao@mail.ipc.ac.cn.

Abstract

High-stability resistance thermometers are crucial for ensuring the reliable comparison and dissemination of the new kelvin, as defined by the Boltzmann constant, particularly at low temperatures. To address this, we have developed standard platinum-cobalt (PtCo) resistance thermometers (with 0.42 % cobalt) specifically for low-temperature applications. These thermometers exhibit exceptional stability with deviations better than 0.2 mK at the water triple point temperature and 0.03 mK near the neon triple point. Their performance was assessed from 4.3 K to 24.5 K, performing calibrations with respect to reference rhodium-iron (RhFe) resistance thermometers. A fifth-order rational function was developed to model the resistance-temperature relationship, which shows higher fitting performance over conventional polynomial fits. This new calibration model achieves a threefold reduction in the standard deviation of the fitting residual, while using one third fewer parameters. Furthermore, long-term transport reliability was confirmed through a 1.5-year international transfer experiment involving three countries and multiple cryogenic cycles, with all measured temperature variations remaining within initial stability limits. These results demonstrate that the newly developed PtCo thermometers could provide a robust, high-accuracy solution for low-temperature metrology, thereby supporting precise calibration and international comparisons under the redefined kelvin.

Keywords: standard platinum cobalt resistance thermometer; thermal cycling; stability; calibration; reliability; international comparison; PtCo

1 Introduction

In 2019, the redefinition of the kelvin, in terms of the Boltzmann constant, enhanced its long-term stability and universality, enabling more accurate temperature measurements from ultra-low to ultra-high temperatures [1]. This advancement has promoted the development and application of primary gas thermometry, linked to the new kelvin. This includes acoustic gas thermometry (AGT) [2-4], dielectric constant gas thermometry (DCGT) [5] and refractive-index gas thermometry (RIGT) [6-12]. However, ensuring consistency among these methods is essential for the global dissemination of the redefined kelvin.

To tackle this challenge, the European Partnership on Metrology project “Dissemination of the redefined kelvin” (DireK-T) has initiated a multilateral comparison of thermodynamic temperature realizations. A key working group within this project is conducting direct comparisons between DCGT, RIGT and AGT in the range from 4 K to 25 K [13]. This effort aims to calibrate capsule-type resistance thermometers (Pt, PtCo, RhFe) with a target standard uncertainty of 0.30 mK, which imposes a stability requirement of better than 0.1 mK on the thermometers.

As a contributing partner within DireK-T, our group has achieved high-accuracy thermodynamic temperature measurements with uncertainties below 0.17 mK [9-11]. We have developed a cryogenic international temperature comparator (CITC) capable of maintaining microkelvin-level stability from 4 K to 25 K [14], and have developed and manufactured Chinese capsule-type standard platinum-cobalt resistance thermometers with stabilities better than 0.1 mK. This work provides a comprehensive characterization of our PtCo thermometers, establishing them as a new and independent source for the international temperature community, alongside the similar PtCo thermometers developed in Japan and commercially available from Chino [16].

In this paper, we evaluate the stability and calibration characteristics of the newly developed PtCo thermometers, demonstrating their suitability to support future international temperature comparisons over extended ranges. The article is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the experimental setup and methodology; Section 3 reports the stability and calibration measurement results; and Section 4 provides concluding remarks and future perspectives.

2 Apparatus and methods

2.1 Alloy wires and thermometers

The Technical Institute of Physics and Chemistry of the Chinese Academy of Sciences (TIPC-CAS) synthesized PtCo alloy samples using a vacuum arc melting furnace under argon protection, with high-purity platinum (99.9999 %) and cobalt (99.995 %) as raw materials. To ensure compositional homogeneity, each ingot was remelted at least five times. This process yielded a PtCo alloy. The addition of a small amount of cobalt to platinum introduces additional resistivity with a significant positive temperature coefficient at low temperatures, thereby effectively extending the thermometer's operational range down to 4 K and below. Consequently, a concentration of 0.42% cobalt by weight was selected to achieve an optimal balance of low-temperature sensitivity and a quasi-linear temperature dependence.

Subsequently, the alloy was drawn into wires of 0.04 mm in diameter by Yunnan Dafang Meter Limited Company, Kunming, China. The wires underwent stress-relief annealing at 700 °C for 10 hours. A spring-structured sensing element was then fabricated by winding the annealed wire into a coiled-coil configuration on a crossed fused-silica frame as in [15]. This element was sealed in a platinum capsule by a glass-to-metal seal through which the four connecting leads emerge; it subsequently underwent a second annealing step at 500 °C for 2 hours. Finally, the capsule was backfilled with 80 kPa of helium gas to enhance heat transfer.

Several capsule-type PtCo resistance thermometers were constructed using this process, each exhibiting a nominal resistance of approximately 100 Ω at the triple point of water ($T_{TPW} = 273.16$ K). As illustrated in Figure 1, the thermometers feature a platinum shell measuring approximately 40 mm in length and 5 mm in outer diameter.

Figure 1. Capsule-type standard platinum–cobalt resistance thermometer developed in this work. Key specifications: cobalt mass fraction 0.42 %; nominal resistance at the triple point of water, 100 Ω ; dimensions, 5 mm (diameter) \times 40 mm (length).

For a PtCo thermometer with a resistance of 100 Ω at T_{TPW} , the measured resistance values are approximately 9 Ω at 25 K and 6.6 Ω at 4.4 K, with corresponding sensitivities of 0.18 Ω /K

and 0.134 Ω/K , respectively. When operated with a 1 mA measuring current, the characterized self-heating effects are approximately 0.5 mK at 25 K and 1.5 mK at 4.4 K. These parameters provide practical reference values for understanding the thermal performance characteristics of the PtCo thermometer.

2.2 Stability test methods

The stability of the PtCo thermometers was systematically evaluated at TIPC-CAS using a dual thermal cycling strategy, comprising liquid nitrogen cycling (77 K-295 K) and low-temperature cycling (5 K-24.5 K). Measurements were conducted at the T_{TPW} and near the triple point of neon ($T_{\text{Ne}} = 24.5561$ K). Thermometers exhibiting the highest level of stability were selected afterwards for accurate low-temperature calibration. The key measurement equipment used for characterizing the PtCo thermometers is summarized in [Table 1](#), and the overall experimental workflow is illustrated in [Figure 2](#).

Table 1. Resistance bridges and standard resistors used for low-temperature cycling and calibration measurements of the standard platinum–cobalt resistance thermometers.

Thermometer label	Resistance bridge	Standard resistor
RIRT_INRiM 1	WIKA (formerly ASL) F18	WIKA 5685A, 10 Ω , SN 049070-02 (for temperature control)
RIRT_NIST	WIKA (formerly ASL) F900	WIKA 5685A, 10 Ω , SN 049070-04
PtCo_X1 PtCo_X3 PtCo_X6 PtCo_X9	Super-thermometer 1594A-1	WIKA 5685A, 10 Ω , SN049070-03
PtCo_X2 PtCo_X4 PtCo_X7	Super-thermometer 1594A-2	WIKA 5685A, 10 Ω , SN045068-03
RIRT_NPL3 PtCo_X5 PtCo_X8	Super-thermometer 1594A-3	WIKA 5685A, 10 Ω , SN045068-01

Figure 2. Schematic of the dual thermal cycling procedure for stability assessment.

2.2.1 Liquid nitrogen thermal cycling

Liquid nitrogen thermal cycling is a widely adopted method for assessing the stability of resistance thermometers due to its relative simplicity and effectiveness [16]. To ensure operational safety and measurement reproducibility, a dedicated liquid nitrogen cycling apparatus was designed and constructed, as illustrated in Figure 3. The system comprises a stainless-steel outer chamber, a high-conductivity copper block, and a vacuum-gas handling system. The thermometers under test are inserted into precisely machined holes in the copper block, which ensures uniform thermal transfer and controlled heating/cooling rates while providing mechanical protection.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of the liquid nitrogen thermal cycling setup.

After sealing the chamber with an indium wire gasket, it was backfilled with approximately 1 kPa of helium gas and then immersed into a liquid nitrogen-filled Dewar. A Cernox resistance thermometer (Model CX-1050 CD-1.4L, S/N X145114), installed on the copper block, was used to monitor the temperature throughout the cycling process using a Keithley 2002 digital multimeter. Once the system stabilized at approximately 77 K for one hour, the apparatus was removed from the Dewar and allowed to warm naturally to ambient temperature, completing one full thermal cycle.

In this work, fifteen thermal cycles were performed. After five cycles, the self-heating characteristics [17] of the resistance thermometers were always evaluated at the T_{TPW} using a standard cell (FLUKE 5901D-G-1427). A reference standard platinum resistance thermometer (Pt25, S/N 5434, 25 Ω), calibrated by the Laboratoire national de métrologie et d'essais (LNE, France), was used to determine T_{90} (International Temperature Scale of 1990) values. Resistance measurements were conducted using an F900 AC resistance bridge and a Tinsley standard resistor (S/N 130702, 100 Ω) housed in a constant-temperature oil bath (MR-5100L). The stability of each PtCo thermometer was assessed at T_{TPW} according to the procedure described in section 2.2.3. Thermometers demonstrating stability better than 0.2 mK were selected for subsequent low-temperature thermal cycling experiments.

2.2.2 Low-temperature thermal cycling

Following the liquid nitrogen thermal cycling, the selected thermometers were installed into a high-stability cryogenic international temperature comparator (CITC) [14], a design conceptually aligned with that described in [18], to perform low-temperature thermal cycling [19, 20]. All thermometers were mounted onto the CITC copper resonator. In this experiment the resonator was used as a comparison block, because of its excellent stability and homogeneity in temperature, as described in [18]. The system was first cooled to 4 K for

20 hours, after which the resonator was heated to a temperature near T_{Ne} . Upon thermal stabilization, the electrical resistances of nine PtCo thermometers were measured sequentially using three resistance bridges (see Table 1). Simultaneously, a separate AC F900 bridge was used to monitor the temperature *via* a reference RhFe resistance thermometer (RIRT_NIST). The resonator was then cooled back to 5 K and held for one hour before being reheated up close to the T_{Ne} . This low-temperature thermal cycling process was repeated five times, after which the stability of the PtCo thermometers at the T_{Ne} was evaluated as detailed in the following section.

Thermometers exhibiting low-temperature stability better than 0.1 mK at T_{Ne} were subsequently removed from the CITC and re-immersed in a TPW cell to reassess their stability. Those found to have maintained stability within 0.2 mK were deemed high-stability thermometers and were selected for further use in low-temperature calibration to further characterize their resistance-temperature (R - T) relationship.

2.2.3 Stability evaluation

The stability of the PtCo resistance thermometers was quantified using the following expressions:

$$\Delta T_{90,i} = \frac{R_i - R_1}{dR/dT_{90}} \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma(\Delta T_{90,i}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\Delta T_{90,i} - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \Delta T_{90,i} \right)^2} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta T_{90,i}$ denotes the temperature variation of the i -th measurement relative to the initial measurement, R_i represents the self-heating-corrected resistance at zero current for the i -th measurement, and dR/dT_{90} is the sensitivity of the thermometer at the triple point of water (T_{TPW}) or neon (T_{Ne}). The subscript i indicates the measurement sequence number, N is the total number of measurements.

2.3 Low-temperature calibration procedure

2.3.1 Calibration methods

The nine PtCo thermometers were calibrated using a steady-state method. Upon stabilizing the resonator temperature to within 30 μK at a given set point, two-current self-heating measurements [17] were sequentially performed using three resistance bridges (see Table 1) to record the resistances of all nine PtCo sensors and the reference thermometer RIRT_NPL3.

Simultaneously, a separate AC F900 bridge was used to monitor the temperature *via* another reference thermometer RIRT_NIST. After completing measurements at one temperature, the resonator was adjusted to a new set point, and the procedure repeated until all designated temperatures had been covered. This process yielded a complete set of (R, T_{90}) data for each thermometer, enabling the determination of its resistance-temperature relationship as detailed in [section 2.3.2](#).

In previous works [11, 21], a stable reference temperature scale, denoted $T_{90,CAS}$, was established and maintained with an uncertainty better than 0.22 mK using a weighted ensemble of three highly stable RhFe resistance thermometers (RIRTs): (1) a 50 Ω RIRT_NIST (S/N 20107, produced by TIPC-CAS/Kunming Dafang Science and Technology Ltd), calibrated by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), USA; (2) two 100 Ω RIRTs, RIRT_NPL1 and RIRT_NPL3 (both Tinsley type, S/N 22242 and 226950), calibrated by the National Physical Laboratory (NPL), UK.

These three RIRTs were recalibrated against $T_{90,CAS}$ with its associated uncertainty $u(T_{90,CAS})$. As the RIRT_NPL1 was dedicated to our single-pressure refractive-index gas thermometry system [9], to ensure the T_{90} traceability in the present study, both RIRT_NIST and RIRT_NPL3 were used to reproduce $T_{90,CAS}$ and $u(T_{90,CAS})$, and served as reference standards for calibrating the nine PtCo thermometers.

2.3.2 Calibration models

In this work, two mathematical models were applied to characterize the resistance-temperature relationship of the nine PtCo thermometers: a conventional polynomial form and a rational function proposed in Ref. [22], which demonstrates superior capability in representing calibration behavior across a wide temperature range for RIRTs.

Model 1: Polynomial

$$T_{90,fit} / \text{K} = \sum_{j=0}^J a_j r^j \quad (3)$$

where J is the degree of the polynomial.

Model 2: Rational function

$$T_{90,fit} / \text{K} = \sum_{k=0}^m p_k r^k \left(1 + \sum_{l=1}^n h_l r^l \right)^{-1} \quad (4)$$

where m and n represent the degrees of the numerator and denominator polynomials in the

rational function, respectively.

$$r = \frac{R - \min(R)}{\max(R) - \min(R)} \quad (5)$$

where R denotes the zero-current resistance in ohm and r is the normalized zero-current resistance.

The fitting parameters a_j , p_k , and h_l are determined by minimizing the objective function:

$$\chi^2 = \sum (T_{90, \text{fit}} / \text{K} - T_{90} / \text{K})_i^2 \quad (6)$$

where $T_{90, \text{fit}}$ are calculated by equation (3) and (4).

2.3.3 Uncertainty evaluation

In this work, the temperature T_{90} is expressed as a function of resistance R , as shown in [equation \(7\)](#). The uncertainty components $u_i(T_{90})$ were therefore evaluated based on variations in resistance (ΔR) and sensitivity $S = dR/dT_{90}$ of the PtCo thermometers as from [equation \(8\)](#). All uncertainty sources were treated as uncorrelated, and the combined standard uncertainty $u_c(T_{90})$ was calculated according to [equation \(9\)](#).

$$T_{90} = f(R) \quad (7)$$

$$u_i(T_{90}) = \Delta T_{90} = |f(R + \Delta R) - f(R)| = |\Delta R \cdot S^{-1}| \quad (8)$$

$$u_c(T_{90}) = \left(\sum u_i^2(T_{90}) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (9)$$

Here, the sensitivity S is derived from the resistance-temperature model given in [equation \(4\)](#).

The following uncertainty components were considered:

- $u(T_{90, \text{ref}})$: Uncertainty from the reference thermometers, determined from the average of $u(T_{90, \text{CAS}})$ reproduced by the two reference RIRTs.
- $u(T_{\text{LTS}})$: Contribution from the low-temperature stability of the PtCo thermometers, evaluated as described in [section 2.2.3](#), with a typical value of 0.037 mK.
- $u(T_{\text{TCS}})$: Uncertainty due to temperature control stability during calibration, with a typical value of 0.015 mK.
- $u(T_{\text{SH}})$, $u(T_{\text{ACB}})$, $u(T_{\text{SR}})$ and $u(T_{\text{OB}})$: Uncertainties originating from the self-heating effect, AC bridge accuracy, standard resistor, and temperature stability of the oil bath, respectively, all estimated *via* [equation \(8\)](#).
- $\sigma(T_{\text{FR}})$: Standard deviation of the fitting residual from the calibration model.

All values represent standard uncertainties.

3 Results and discussion

Based on the experimental apparatus and methodologies outlined in section 2, comprehensive evaluations were conducted to characterize the stability, low-temperature calibration performance, and long-term transport reliability of the capsule-type PtCo resistance thermometers. The following sections present and describe the results of these investigations, highlighting robustness and measurement precision of the PtCo thermometers under the examined conditions.

3.1 Stability performance

3.1.1 Stability at the triple point of water

Eleven PtCo thermometers with 0.42 wt% cobalt was fabricated after multiple process optimizations. Following stability testing at T_{TPW} , two thermometers were excluded for exceeding the 0.2 mK stability criterion, exhibiting deviations of 1.1 mK and 0.23 mK, respectively. The remaining nine thermometers, which all met the T_{TPW} stability requirement, were installed in the CITC and subsequently tested at T_{Ne} .

Figure 4 shows the stability performance of the nine capsule-type PtCo resistance thermometers at the T_{TPW} . The observed stability incorporates two principal components: (1) the stability of the TPW cell itself, monitored using a reference standard platinum resistance thermometer (Pt25), which exhibited a typical variation of 0.04 mK, and (2) the stability of the PtCo thermometers at T_{TPW} , converted to temperature variation *via* their sensitivity dR/dT_{90} , with values below 0.16 mK. The overall stability of the PtCo thermometers ranged from 0.08 mK to 0.17 mK, well within the target stability requirement of 0.2 mK at the T_{TPW} .

Figure 4. Stability of the nine capsule-type platinum-cobalt resistance thermometers at the triple point of water.

3.1.2 Stability near the triple point of neon

Having satisfied the stability requirement at the T_{TPW} , the nine PtCo thermometers underwent further stability evaluations at a temperature close to the T_{Ne} . The results are presented in Figure 5. As at the T_{TPW} , the overall stability incorporates two primary components: (1) the contribution from temperature control stability, taken as the maximum temperature control stability observed during cycling (0.0275 mK), and the repeatability of the RIRT_NIST readings, expressed as the standard deviation of its T_{90} values at T_{Ne} (0.004 mK), resulting in a combined stability estimate of 0.028 mK; and (2) the stability of the PtCo thermometer resistances at the T_{Ne} , which corresponds to a temperature variation below 0.007 mK. The resulting overall stability of the PtCo thermometers is 0.030 mK, well within the target stability of 0.1 mK at the T_{Ne} .

Figure 5. Stability of the nine capsule-type platinum-cobalt resistance thermometers near the triple point of neon.

3.2 Low-temperature calibration performance

The nine PtCo thermometers demonstrated high stability both at the T_{TPW} and near the T_{Ne} , fulfilling the prerequisite for high-accuracy calibration. Consequently, they were subjected to comprehensive low-temperature calibration across the range of 4.3 K to 24.5 K.

3.2.1 Resistance–Temperature relationship

Using the steady-state calibration method described in section 2.3, two-current self-heating measurements were performed for the nine PtCo thermometers at 63 temperature points between 4.3 K and 24.5 K, with a step size of approximately 0.35 K.

Figure 6 shows the zero-current resistances and normalized zero-current resistances of the

thermometers as a function of the reference temperature T_{90} . All thermometers exhibit similar resistance trends, particularly in normalized form, indicating that a unified calibration model may be suitable for this type of thermometers.

Figure 6. Zero-current resistance(a) and normalized zero-current resistance(b) of the nine capsule-type platinum-cobalt resistance thermometers from 4.3 K to 24.5 K. Points are connected by straight lines as a guide to the eye.

To accurately characterize the R - T relationship, the two models, polynomial (equation (3)) and rational function (equation (4)), were optimized and compared. The fitting procedure aimed to minimize the residual standard deviation, with a target value near 0.05 mK consistent with the lowest thermodynamic temperature uncertainty reported in Ref. [10] over the range of 5 K to 24.5 K. As illustrated in Figure 7 for thermometer PtCo_X1, the optimal polynomial degree was determined to be $J = 15$ (corresponding to 16 parameters), while the rational function achieved comparable accuracy with only $m = 5$ and $n = 5$ (in total 11 parameters). Consistent results were observed across all the eight thermometers under study.

Figure 7. Optimization results of polynomial (a) and rational functions (b) for PtCo_X1 thermometer. Points are connected by straight lines as a guide to the eye.

A comparative evaluation of the two models is illustrated in Figure 8. The rational function achieves a reduction in the number of parameters by approximately one-third compared to the polynomial model, while simultaneously improving fitting accuracy. Specifically, it reduces both the fitting residuals and their standard deviation by an average factor of three across all thermometers. This outcome aligns with findings reported in Ref. [22], which employed a rational function to characterize the resistance-temperature relationship of a RIRT over a broad temperature range. These results demonstrate that the fifth-order rational function provides a compact, highly accurate, and unified model framework for describing the R - T behavior of PtCo thermometers. The corresponding parameters of the rational function for each thermometer are provided in Table 2.

(a) Fitting residuals of PtCo_X1 thermometer (b) Standard deviation of fitting residuals

Figure 8. Comparison of fitting residuals (a) and standard deviation of fitting residuals (b) between the optimal polynomial ($J = 15$) and the optimal rational function ($m = 5, n = 5$) for all nine PtCo thermometers.

Table 2. Fitted parameters of the fifth-order rational function ($m = 5, n = 5$) for the standard platinum-cobalt resistance thermometers.

	PtCo_X1	PtCo_X2	PtCo_X3	PtCo_X4	PtCo_X5	PtCo_X6	PtCo_X7	PtCo_X8	PtCo_X9
<i>k</i>	p_k (optimal numerator degree $m = 5$)								
0	500.16827588	491.19415712	527.26675131	571.78567183	517.32948102	496.14180291	656.74581648	558.27797215	460.31434169
1	34.61160232	31.16467498	39.67972981	48.45812109	37.95641637	37.38519540	60.59907172	44.89708850	24.96029056
2	90.30588591	89.59969094	93.95142197	97.57179963	92.69514359	90.21052880	105.88339584	96.18601429	86.67586731
3	12.71509005	12.33556570	13.24548175	14.39181293	13.05221101	12.70047596	16.02368762	14.04428237	11.50529637
4	2.30985772	2.24218880	2.34293908	2.28252260	2.33737794	2.33654588	2.23668523	2.27892614	2.31264380
5	4.39324207	4.39323613	4.39323758	4.39324390	4.39323792	4.39323594	4.39324519	4.39324100	4.39323752
<i>l</i>	h_l (optimal denominator degree $n = 5$)								
1	-3.37235128	-3.38303904	-3.40665209	-3.45343108	-3.39385382	-3.37225687	-3.54085926	-3.44112719	-3.33425319
2	11.14275568	11.10445807	11.43330646	11.83660598	11.32580605	11.12916691	12.57974286	11.70423115	10.76564615
3	-11.35635926	-11.35376076	-11.69723984	-12.23602088	-11.56379353	-11.28108668	-13.24040913	-12.07143412	-10.91844449
4	22.66431992	22.29566515	23.86593087	25.77246936	23.41554947	22.59755324	29.25892153	25.11959067	20.92988713
5	5.73386986	5.60525339	6.07372591	6.67248312	5.96007787	5.68534633	7.81999326	6.52768232	5.19300024

3.2.2 Evaluation of calibration uncertainty

After determining the optimal calibration model, the fifth-order rational function with $m = 5$ and $n = 5$, a detailed uncertainty budget was evaluated for each thermometer following the methodology outlined in [section 2.3.3](#).

[Figure 9](#) shows the uncertainty components for thermometer PtCo_X1 over the temperature range from 4.3 K to 24.5 K. The two dominant sources of uncertainty originate from the reference thermometer and the stability of the PtCo thermometer itself. The third, fourth and fifth most significant contributions arise from the self-heating effect, temperature control stability and standard deviation of the fitting residuals. In contrast, uncertainties related to the AC bridge, standard resistor and oil bath are negligible.

[Table 3](#) provides a detailed uncertainty budget for all nine thermometers at 5 K. The results indicate that the reference thermometer uncertainty and the stability of the PtCo sensors are the primary factors influencing calibration accuracy. These findings highlight the importance of high-accuracy thermodynamic temperature references and highly stable resistance thermometers for ensuring reliable comparisons between different primary thermometry methods, such as those employed within the DireK-T project to accurately disseminate the new kelvin.

These behaviors are consistent across all nine PtCo thermometers. The combined calibration standard uncertainty remains below 0.25 mK throughout the entire temperature range, meeting the target uncertainty of 0.3 mK set by the DireK-T project [\[13\]](#). The stability and low calibration uncertainty demonstrated by the Chinese PtCo thermometers confirm their suitability for high-precision calibration and international comparisons in low-temperature metrology.

[Figure 9](#). Calibration uncertainty components for PtCo_X1 using the fifth-order rational function between 4.3 K and 24.5 K. The low-temperature stability of the thermometer was taken equal to the value determined near the triple point of neon in [section 3.1.2](#).

Table 3. Uncertainty budget for the calibration of the standard platinum-cobalt resistance thermometers near 5 K. All values are given in millikelvin (mK).

Thermometer Label	PtCo_X1	PtCo_X2	PtCo_X3	PtCo_X4	PtCo_X5	PtCo_X6	PtCo_X7	PtCo_X8	PtCo_X9
Uncertainty component									
Reference thermometer, $u(T_{90,\text{ref}})$	0.091	0.091	0.091	0.091	0.091	0.091	0.091	0.091	0.091
Stability of thermometer ¹ $u(T_{\text{LTS}})$	0.029	0.029	0.029	0.029	0.029	0.029	0.029	0.029	0.029
Temperature control stability, $\sigma(T_{\text{TCS}})$	0.015	0.015	0.016	0.016	0.015	0.016	0.015	0.016	0.015
Self-heating effect, $u(T_{\text{SH}})$	0.016	0.015	0.017	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.015	0.016	0.015
AC bridge accuracy, $u(T_{\text{ACB}})$	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
Standard resistor, $u(T_{\text{SR}})$	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
Temperature stability of oil bath, $\sigma(T_{\text{OB}})$	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
Standard deviation of fitting residual, $\sigma(T_{\text{FR}})$	0.012	0.012	0.014	0.013	0.012	0.013	0.015	0.014	0.011
Overall standard calibration uncertainty	0.099	0.098							

¹ Note: The low-temperature stability value was taken from the measurement near the triple point of neon, as determined in section 3.1.2.

3.3 Long-term transport reliability

Following their initial calibration in 2023, two thermometers (PtCo_X2 and PtCo_X6) were randomly selected to evaluate long-term reliability after several travels. These sensors travelled from TIPC-CAS (China) to LNE (France), then to INRiM (Italy), and back to LNE, undergoing two cooldown cycles in different cryostats before returning to TIPC-CAS in 2025. Their performance was re-evaluated at the T_{TPW} and near the T_{Ne} using the CITC.

Figure 10 presents the long-term transport reliability results of PtCo_X2 and PtCo_X6 at T_{TPW} and near T_{Ne} over a period of 1.5 years, which included transfers among the three countries and thermal cycling in three different cryostats. PtCo_X2 exhibited better performance, with the observed temperature difference $\Delta T = T_{2023} - T_{2025}$ equal to approximately 0.14 mK at the T_{TPW} and 0.023 mK near the T_{Ne} , both consistent with its recorded stability of 0.16 mK and 0.028 mK, respectively. As for PtCo_X6, the observed temperature difference was approximately 0.11 mK at the T_{TPW} , consistent with its stability of 0.14 mK, and 0.046 mK near the T_{Ne} , remaining within twice its stability value (0.029 mK). These results demonstrate the good mechanical and thermal robustness of the PtCo thermometers, displaying their reliability for long-term international transport and use in metrological applications, such as bilateral and multilateral comparisons.

(a) Temperature difference at T_{TPW}

(b) Temperature difference near T_{Ne}

Figure 10. Long-term transport reliability of thermometers PtCo_X2 and PtCo_X6 at the triple point of water and near the triple point of neon, evaluated over a period of 1.5 years including transfer among three countries and thermal cycling in three different cryostats.

4 Conclusion and perspectives

This study demonstrates that the newly developed standard PtCo resistance thermometers have high stability and measurement uncertainty performance, making them highly suitable for precision metrology in the low-temperature regime. The sensors exhibit stability better than

0.2 mK at the triple point of water and 0.03 mK near the triple point of neon, meeting the stringent requirements for the dissemination of the kelvin under its new definition.

The thermometers were calibrated between 4.3 K and 24.5 K using traceable rhodium-iron resistance thermometers as reference standards. A unified 11-parameter rational function was developed to characterize the resistance-temperature relationship of PtCo sensors. Despite using one-third fewer parameters than conventional polynomial models, this function achieved a threefold improvement in fitting accuracy. The overall calibration uncertainty is maintained below 0.25 mK, which meets the 0.3 mK uncertainty target specified by the DireK-T project.

Long-term transport reliability was confirmed *via* a 1.5-year international transfer campaign across three countries, incorporating multiple cryogenic cycles. Temperature variations of the tested PtCo thermometers are within their initial stability limits at both T_{TPW} and T_{Ne} . These excellent performances demonstrate the superior capability of these PtCo thermometers and calibration models for high-accuracy low temperature metrology.

Future efforts will focus on evaluating the long-term stability of PtCo thermometers and extending the calibration range down to 0.65 K, the lower limit of the ITS-90, using a newly developed cryogenic measurement system.

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